

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL CREATIVITY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Zubaydullayeva Zarina Erkinovna

Tashkent Academic Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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Annotation: This article deals with the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the differences between old and contemporary teaching methods, the types of modern methods used in the methodology of teaching a foreign language and the ways of using them in a creative way.

Key words: descriptive method, non-linguistic university. method, creative analysis.

The huge changes taking place in the life of our society are affecting all areas, as well as the process of higher education. The breakdown of old forms of social relations and the emergence of a new democratic way of life require the creative activity of the individual. By improving the education system in the country, great attention is paid to the training of mature, well-rounded, independent-minded, strong-willed, dedicated and enterprising personnel. The educational process plays a leading role in the training of qualified, competitive personnel. In this way, the essence of creative teaching is one of the most crucial aspects of an active learning process aimed at expanding the educational opportunities of professionals and the formation of a particular worldview.

Considered as an integral part of EFL (English as a Foreign Language) or ESL (English as a Second Language) teaching, the topic of teaching English for Specific Purposes deserves special consideration. From a methodological perspective, but also in terms of its purposefulness, the field of ESP is situated at the border between academic subjects, at the intersection of specialized scientific knowledge and linguistic competence. Hutchinson and Waters [1] argue that the beginning of ESP can be traced back to the end of the second world war, when due to the rising of commerce, the importance of speaking languages had risen in importance. What was different compared to the already existent and established patterns of language teaching was the purposefulness of the teaching process. It was for the first time in the history of language teaching when the ultimate goal did not have to do with high culture, with achieving social status or to the ability to read classic literature. This time, the goal was rooted in a much more practical soil: the language teaching process was meant to equip learners with linguistic competences which would make

them function adequately on the labor market and in a specific work environment.

In encouraging students to learn a foreign language, the most essential requirement for teachers is creativity. Since there are students who are interested in different spheres in a classroom, teachers should be able to teach English in an integrated way with other subjects and this, in turn, can help students to improve critical-thinking skills, motivation and engagement, and start to understand the role of creativity in developing new scientific knowledge. At the classroom level, the incorporation of teaching practices that promote creativity can lead to positive changes in student behavior, social skills, self-esteem, motivation, and academic achievement. The benefits of incorporating creativity in the classroom have been reviewed, but a trend surfaces when researchers examine teachers' perceptions of creativity as well as their implementation of creativity philosophies in the regular education classroom.

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